

Recommended citation: Virta, U., & Järvinen, H. (2020). Survey on Engineering Ethics. In van der Veen, J., van Hattum-Janssen, N., Järvinen, H.-M., de Laet, T., & ten Dam, I. (Eds.), *Engaging Engineering Education. SEFI 48th Annual Conference* (pp. 1159-1169). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Enschede, The Netherlands. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.14654215](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14654215).

SURVEY ON ENGINEERING ETHICS

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ABSTRACT

The raise of artificial intelligence applications has awoken growing interest in ethical issues relating to engineering. However, this AI-focused trend does not address ethical issues that are present in traditional engineering work. Further, many publications discuss the ethics of technology from outsiders' point of view, not as the ethics of professionals in engineering. In this paper, we describe ongoing research on engineering ethics from the engineers' point of view.

The main objective of the study is to identify ethical problems that engineers of different disciplines encounter in their everyday work. Results will be used to formulate the contents of ethical studies for engineering education, with the final goal of suggesting how ethical contents can be embedded in engineering education.

Secondary usage for the results is to suggest how the Association of Academic Engineers and Architects in Finland should support its members with their real-world ethical questions.

The goal of this paper is to describe the questionnaire designed for the purposes above and invite fellow researchers to conduct similar surveys outside Finland.

Conference Key areas: Sustainability and ethics. Engineering curriculum design.

Keywords: engineering ethics

1 INTRODUCTION

Engineers work with many of the core functionalities that shape our society. In some fields, such as artificial intelligence, the importance of ethical issues has been recognized as something affecting the engineering work and high profile issues are also publicly discussed. However, such discussion does not address ethical issues that are present in more traditional engineering work [1]. There exist several ethical codes for engineers like the Archimedean Oath [2] or the codes of IEEE [3] and ACM [4]. These codes describe the ethics but do not help engineers when an active ethical issue is at hand.

The questionnaire described in this paper aims to better understanding of what kind of ethical issues engineers encounter during their professional life and how the ethical issues are handled in the workplaces. Understanding the nature of ethical issues can then be used to design

how ethical contents can be embedded in engineering education in such ways that it supports the professional life of the future engineers. The results are used to help the Association of Academic Engineers and Architects in Finland (TEK) to offer support for its members with real-world ethical questions and problems. The survey described here will be conducted for about 5000 members TEK during 2020.

The structure of the paper follows the structure of the survey. The questionnaire is composed of two main sections:

- A common part for all respondents about ethical attitudes the engineers have, general demographic questions, ethical support and ethics in education. These questions are discussed in Section 2.
- Secondly, a case section, where respondents can describe ethical issue or issues they have encountered in their professional life. The case specific section is given to respondents who indicate that they want to describe encountered ethical issue in more detail. These questions are introduced in Section 3.

The reason having separate part of cases is to encourage respondents who have not encountered specific ethical issues to answer the questionnaire.

2 THE COMMON PART OF THE QUESTIONNAIRE

The common part of the survey consists of three sections: about the general ethical attitudes of the engineers, background information about the respondents, and post questions about ethical issues present in respondents' studies and what kind of support the respondents' would like to have in ethics issues.

The first and second part of common questions form the first part in the whole survey, then follows the case part described in Section 3, and the last part is the post questions of the common questions.

2.1 Ethical attitudes

The survey begins with questions about the general ethical attitudes of engineers. To measure engineers' sensitivity to ethical issues, a selected group of questions was taken from the ethical sensitivity scale by K. Tirri and P. Nokelainen [5]. Original scale included 28 questions divided into seven categories. To reduce the total length of the survey, only 14 questions were selected. The selected questions included all questions from categories "Preventing social bias", "Generating interpretations and options", and "Identifying the consequences of actions and options". In addition, two questions were selected from category "Working with interpersonal and group differences" as they focused on identifying or reacting to ethical issues. The selected questions are presented in Table 1 with original identifiers from [5]. Question es7_27 is modified to use term "work" instead of "school". The ethical questions are collected into Table 1. All ethical sensitivity scale questions should be answered with a five-point Likert scale, where one is "totally disagree" and five "totally agree" [5].

Table 1: Selected ethical sensitivity scale questions [5].

Identifier	Question
es4_15	When I am working on ethical problems, I consider the impact of my decisions on other people.
es4_16	I try to consider other peoples' needs, even in situations concerning my own benefits.

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Table 1 – continued from previous page

Question	Options
es5_17	I recognize my own bias when I take a stand on ethical issues.
es5_18	I realize that I am tied to certain prejudices when I assess ethical issues.
es5_19	I try to control my own prejudices when making ethical evaluations.
es5_20	When I am resolving ethical problems, I try to take a position evolving out of my own social status.
es6_21	I contemplate on the consequences of my actions when making ethical decisions.
es6_22	I ponder on different alternatives when aiming at the best possible solution to an ethically problematic situation.
es6_23	I am able to create many alternative ways to act when I face ethical problems in my life.
es6_24	I believe there are several right solutions to ethical problems.
es7_25	I notice that there are ethical issues involved in human interaction.
es7_26	I see a lot of ethical problems around me.
es7_27*	I am aware of the ethical issues I face at work.
es7_28	I am better than other people in recognizing new and current ethical problems.

2.2 Background questions

The demographic question section includes the personal questions about birth year, the year of Master's degree or equivalent, the alma mater, the degree programme for Master's degree, gender, and position in current workplace. In addition, there are questions related to the respondent's current or the most recent workplace, that are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Workplace-related background questions.

Question	Options	
B1: How many people currently work at your workplace, or your most recent workplace?	1 – 5 21 – 50 251 – 1000	6 – 20 51 – 250 over 1000
B2: Does your current or most recent workplace have official procedure to bring forth ethical issues or problems? Select all applicable.	No Yes, designated contact person Yes, anonymous channel Do not know	Yes, ethics committee Yes, through regular chain of superiors Yes, other; please specify.
B3: Does your current or most recent workplace have official procedure to address and solve ethical problems or to their after-care? Select all applicable.	No Yes, democratic processes of employer and employees. Yes, superior Yes, other; please specify.	Yes, committee or named group who gives statement Yes, peer support between coworkers Yes, support person Do not know

2.3 Post questions

All respondents are asked three post questions to map the general status of ethical issues in engineering work and studies. The first question P1 is about the need for support in ethical questions. Its answers are collected with the matrix which is used in questions S25 and T25 of case studies, too. Respondents select the desired types of support with the wanted providers. Options for both types of support and providers of support are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Matrix headers for questions P1, S25 and T25

Providers of support	Types of support
Company or organization itself	Support personnel during decision making Ethical board or committee
Provided by the company or organization but produced by external actor such as consultant or occupational health care	Educational material such as example cases and their solutions Educational material such as ethical codes
Labor union	Organized peer support
Self provided	Legal services
Other, what?	Support personnel for after care Other, what?

Our hypothesis is that ethical questions are not clearly present in engineering studies. Question P2 is about the state of ethical issues in respondent's studies and P3 is asking respondent's opinion about how to discuss ethical issues in studies. Answers to these questions are used as a basis when making a suggestion how to take ethics into account in engineering education. The post questions are presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Post questions

Question	Options
P1: What kind of support you think is needed in general?	The matrix of Table 3.
P2: Were ethical questions or issues discussed during your studies?	Separately as ethical issues or on a dedicated course Combined with other topics. Not discussed at all.
P3: How you would have liked ethical questions or issues discussed during studies?	Open answer.

3 THE CASE PART OF THE QUESTIONNAIRE

The case specific section contains questions about ethical issues the respondent has encountered during their professional life. The respondent can select between "single case" or "type example", or both. The respondent can describe several cases of both types. Here the "single case" refers to a situation where the respondent wants to describe a specific incident or ethical issue they have encountered. "Type example" can be used when the respondent has encountered similar ethical issue multiple times during their professional life, either within one organization or at different organizations. The selected type affects some of the questions.

This section describes the case specific questions. Questions are divided into four categories: The time frame of the issue, the field, type and description of the issue, the issue detection, and the issue solving process. Questions posed in each category are described in corresponding sections. Each section describes both single case and type example questions.

Some ethical issues can be prevalent and are encountered multiple times by engineers during their professional life. Separation of type examples from single cases allows to more easily identify what are the common types of ethical issues an engineer can encounter. In addition, it should make the answering easier for the respondent. As the single case and the type

example share many of the questions, both cases are discussed in this section.

Questions are given ID starting with S for single cases and T for type examples. As question sets for these categories share many questions that are exactly the same or very similar, the equivalent questions will share the same numbering for both the single case and the type examples. As there are also questions that apply only for single cases or type examples, there are missing numbers in both set of questions.

3.1 The time frame of the issue

To determine if the encountered single case issues are recent or old, and if they were short-lived situations or continued for prolonged time, questions described in Table 5 are asked from respondents. The age of the problem is used to see if the nature of problems has changed over the time. The duration is used to find out how long the situation was accepted.

With type examples, the respondent might have encountered the issue multiple times in different organizations over the years, so type example does not have equivalent questions for S1 and S2. However, it does have type example unique question T3 to help to evaluate, how prevalent the issues are and if it is common for engineers to encounter similar problems during their professional life. Understanding what the commonly encountered issues are, allows targeting education and support for those kinds of cases.

Table 5: Questions on the issue time frame category.

Question	Options	
S1: How long ago the case happened / started?	0 – 5 years ago Over 10 years ago	5 – 10 years ago
S2: How long the ethically questionable situation continued?	Days Months Do not know	Weeks Years
T3: How often you have encountered ethical issue of this kind?	Couple of times Often Habitually, or it is the prevalent way of acting.	Once in a while Do not know or prefer not to answer

3.2 The field, type and description of the issue

The issue field and type category in Table 6 includes questions S/T4-S/T7 about the nature of the ethical issue and field it was encountered in. The purpose is to recognize the area of engineering in question. As the problem can arise from application area, which is expected to often happen e.g. in information technology, this information is also collected.

With the type example, it is also important to distinct whether the issue was encountered multiple times in the same organization as that allows organization to change their policies, or if it was in different organizations. Further, separating these two allows us to understand if the issue is an indicator of single organization having problems, or if the ethical issue is prevalent in the industry. For this purpose, question T8 was added for the type examples only.

Last two questions ask for the description of the issue itself and its working environment. Last question for the type example allows several alternatives to be answered.

Table 6: Questions on the issue field and type category.

Question	Options
S4, T4: Was the ethical issue related to (select all applicable)	Working terms, conditions, management or human resources (General workplace ethics, GWE) Behavior or attitudes at workplace (GWE) Job applying situations, hiring (GWE) Contracts (Professional ethics, PE) Conflicts of interest, positions of trust (GWE) Specific product, its operation or features (PE) Work processes (PE) Marketing, competitive tendering, customer acquisition (PE) Engineering work and its core questions or consequences (PE) Other, please specify.
S5, T5: What kind of potential or actualized negative consequences this ethical issue / problem caused or could have caused? (Select all applicable)	Life, health or safety related Decrease in well-being, discomfort Regarding equal or fair treatment of humans Financial consequences, either for company or organization, its customers or society as whole Environment or nature related Confidentiality or (human) privacy related Customer or client could not get product or service they purchased/contracted Deception, manipulation or exploitation Endangering person's autonomy or their possibility to do their own choices Breaking decrees or laws Other, please specify,
S6, T6: What field/line of work you were representing?	Options for this question should include country appropriate technical domains listed.
S7, T7: Describe the field or context of the ethical issue itself, if it differs from the previous question.	Open question
T8: Have you encountered issue of this type in multiple organizations or mainly multiple times within same organization?	In one organization In multiple organizations
S9, T9: Describe in more detail what kind of situation was and what happened.	Open question
S10: What kind of working/professional environment the ethical problem was present? Choose the most fitting option. T10: What kind of working/professional environment the ethical problem was present? Choose all options that fit.	Project in or with private company Production Consulting Teaching or research Public organization (government, municipalities, church, societies) Other, please specify.

3.3 The issue detection

For understanding the emotional condition of the engineer, it is important to know when the ethical issue was first recognized. It is also very interesting to find out, who noticed the ethical problem and how it was brought forward. People might be afraid of raising ethical issues into discussion, hence information on possible attitude changes to the whistle-blower is a relevant thing to gather. The questions related to the detection of the issue are listed in Table 7.

For understanding if and how organizations and individuals learn from previously encountered ethical issues, there are some questions specific for type examples added (T12, T14, T17) or altered (S11, S13, S16) to identify, how the behaviors change when encountering the subsequent cases of the issue type. This can open up possibilities to explore, if education could pre-emptively help the individuals and organizations to build processes to handle ethical issues. It is also possible that instead of learning, desensitization or frustration rises, which is why change in attitude changes is collected.

Table 7: Questions in Issue detection category

Question	Options
S11: When the ethical issue was noticed or when you yourself recognized it? Choose most fitting option. T11: When the ethical issue was noticed or when you yourself recognized it for the first time? Choose most fitting option.	Before starting or committing to operation (for example: before signing contract, before starting internal project, ...) During planning or specifying the operation In the middle of implementing After completion but before deployment During deployment or shortly after Later / Afterwards Do not know
T12: Was the issue noticed, or did you notice the issue earlier or faster on the subsequent times the issue was encountered?	Yes, always Yes, most of the times No Do not know
S13: Who noticed the ethical issue? T13: Who noticed the ethical issue for the first time?	You yourself Member of work community / someone working with the project Other stakeholder in the project External actor or public officer Other, please specify. Do not know or prefer not to answer
T14: Who typically noticed the issue on the subsequent times this kind of issue was encountered? Select all applicable.	Same as above You yourself Member of work community / someone working with the project Other stakeholder in the project External actor or public officer Other, please specify. Do not know or prefer not to answer
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Table 7 – continued from previous page

Question	Options
S15: How the ethical issue was brought forth? Select all applicable.	It was not brought forth at all During private conversations with colleagues During private conversations with responsible person In project meeting / similar session Through official channels Anonymously (for example suggestion box or other anonymous means) Other, please specify.
S16: How did the attitudes of the work community or employer change for the person/persons who brought forth the ethical issue? T16: How did the attitudes of the work community or employer change for the person/persons who brought forth the ethical issue for the first time?	To very negative, possibly also concrete consequences such as firing the person/persons To negative, but mostly social consequences such as resentment or disapproval Attitudes did not change (neither to positive nor to negative) To positive, but mostly social consequences such as respect or gratitude To very positive, possibly also concrete consequences such as rewards Incoherent attitude changes: some attitudes changed towards positive, some towards negative None of the above / Do not know Issue was not brought forth, so no changes.
T17: How did the attitude changes on subsequent times compared to the first encounter?	Change was more positive Did not change in substantial manner Change was more negative Do not know

3.4 The issue solving process

It is important to find out the reaction of the decision makers to the problem and how they decide to handle it. It is also worthwhile to see if the decision was in line with the organizations policy and the culture. Since many engineers are themselves decision makers, this information is also collected. There might be bias in answers that show ethically positive reaction if the respondent was making the decision themselves.

The available and wanted support are asked to see their need in engineers' work. The support wanted and the potential provider of the support are asked using the matrix introduced in Table 3. These questions are important for our research partner, TEK.

As with the issue detection for the type example, it is important to understand, if previously encountered issues cause lasting effects on the organization's or individual's capabilities to handle similar ethical issues. In cases where the issue was encountered in different organizations, it is impossible to determine if organizations have revised their processes. However, it allows exploring, if organizations differ in their behavior when they encounter similar problems. To gather information about these, there are several varied or type-example-only questions. The last question asks for permission to use the case description in educational material if it is made anonymous and sanitized. All questions on this category are gathered to Table 8.

Table 8: Questions in Issue solving process category.

Question	Options
<p>S18: What was the reaction of the decision makers to solve or handle the ethical issue / problem? Select all applicable.</p> <p>T18: What was the reaction of the decision makers to solve or handle the ethical issue / problem for the first time? Select all applicable.</p>	<p>Negative reaction towards bringing it forth</p> <p>Issue was ignored or buried</p> <p>Issue was discussed on but actions were not taken or the issue was left to hang in the air</p> <p>Policies or practices were changed</p> <p>It was decided to withdraw from the situation or project, or refused to join or participate in it</p> <p>Do not know or prefer not to answer</p> <p>Issue was not brought forth, so it was not handled.</p>
<p>T19a in one organization: Did the organization's reaction change on subsequent times?</p>	<p>Did not change.</p> <p>Did change, how?</p> <p>Do not know or prefer not to answer.</p>
<p>T19b in multiple organizations: Did the reactions between different organization differ from each other?</p>	<p>Not substantially.</p> <p>Yes, how?</p> <p>Do not know or prefer not to answer.</p>
<p>S20: How was the decision made?</p> <p>T20: How was the decision made for the first time?</p>	<p>Person(s) responsible made the decision</p> <p>Consensus was reached or vote was taken</p> <p>There was not clear decision</p> <p>Issue was not addressed at all</p> <p>Do not know or prefer not to answer</p>
<p>T21a in one organization: Did the decision making process change during the subsequent times?</p>	<p>Did not change.</p> <p>Did change, how?</p> <p>Do not know or prefer not to answer.</p>
<p>T21b in different organizations: Did the decision making process differ between organizations?</p>	<p>Not substantially.</p> <p>Yes, how?</p> <p>Do not know or prefer not to answer.</p>
<p>S22: Was the reaction to the ethical issue in line with the organization's normal culture or did it differ from it?</p>	<p>Yes</p> <p>No</p> <p>Do not know or prefer not to answer</p>
<p>S23: Were you the decision maker or person responsible during the ethical issue case?</p> <p>T23: Were you usually the decision maker or person responsible during the ethical issue case?</p>	<p>Yes, alone</p> <p>Yes, as a part of a group</p> <p>No</p> <p>Do not know or prefer not to answer</p>
<p>S24, T24: What kind of support was available in solving the ethical problem or issue? Select all applicable.</p>	<p>None</p> <p>Support types from Table 3</p> <p>Do not know or prefer not to answer</p>
<p>S25, T25: What kind of support you would have wanted?</p>	<p>The matrix of Table 3.</p>
<p>Continued on next page</p>	

Table 8 – continued from previous page

Question	Options
S26, T26: Have you done any personal decisions or changes because of this event? Select all applicable.	No Switched workplace or resigned Switched department inside organization Took legal actions or filed police report Complained to administrative agency Contacted media Changed your own practices Prefer not to answer
S27, T27: If the case description is made anonymous and sanitized, can it be used as an example in ethical material?	Yes No

4 DISCUSSION

This questionnaire was to be sent to about 5000 engineers in Finland during April 2020. Unfortunately, due to the coronavirus pandemic, the actual implementation of the questionnaire is rescheduled to August.

However, one motivation for the early publishing of the questionnaire is to call for other researchers to do the same or at least close enough research in their area to get better understanding if the problems encountered differ in other countries or areas either in Europe or worldwide.

At this stage, we feel the survey will give answers to the following main questions:

- what kind of ethical issues engineers have encountered
- how the employer and the working environment reacted to the person raising the issue
- how the decision maker reacted to the issue itself
- if there are any systemic processes to handle the cases
- are the typical cases single occasions or way to behave
- what kind of ethical support engineers would like to have?

The results of the questionnaire are used as a basis for future work in finding the suitable topics and ways to include ethical issues in engineering education. Firstly, it is important to distinguish if engineers do not recognize ethical issues, if they do not know how to resolve the issues or do not see the issues worthwhile to resolve, or if the working environment is resisting. Each one of these require a different set of skills from the engineers. The nature the core issues can affect the way it should be approached during education: through separate courses, integrating teaching into existing courses or project works or as a part of the thesis. There might be problems of a different kind, depending on the engineering areas: we expect the problems e.g. in civil engineering, process industry, and information technology have different emphasis. The value of real life examples is also expected to be higher for educational material, compared with invented examples.

The other usage is for TEK. Their interest is to see the ethical problems faced in everyday engineering work, and how the association can support its members in these cases.

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